

Effect of rectal ozone insufflation on clinical and laboratory outcomes in critically ill COVID-19 patients in the intensive care unit

Yoğun bakımda ağır COVID-19 hastalarında rektal ozon insüflasyonunun klinik ve laboratuvar bulgularına etkisi

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ABSTRACT

Aim: To evaluate the effects of rectal ozone insufflation as an adjunctive therapy in critically ill patients hospitalized in the intensive care unit (ICU) with severe COVID-19 pneumonia.

Material and Methods: This single-blind, randomized, prospective clinical study included 60 adult patients with severe COVID-19 admitted to the ICU between May 15 and July 7, 2020. Patients were randomly assigned to either the rectal ozone insufflation (ROI) group (n=30) or the control group (n=30). In addition to the standard COVID-19 treatment protocol, the ROI group received rectal ozone insufflation (30 µg/250 mL) every 12 hours for 14 days. Primary outcomes included changes in C-reactive protein (CRP) levels, oxygen saturation, Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS), and Sequential Organ Failure Assessment (SOFA) scores. Secondary outcomes were duration of intubation, length of ICU and hospital stay, and mortality.

Results: Baseline demographic and clinical characteristics were comparable between groups. In the ROI group, CRP levels significantly decreased at the end of treatment compared to baseline (p=0.001), whereas no significant change was observed in the control group. GCS scores significantly improved and SOFA scores significantly decreased in the ROI group (p<0.05). The proportion of patients requiring intubation and overall mortality were significantly lower in the ROI group compared to controls (p<0.05).

Conclusion: Rectal ozone insufflation as an adjunct to standard therapy may contribute to reduced inflammation, improved clinical scores, and lower mortality in critically ill COVID-19 patients. Larger multicenter studies are required to confirm these findings.

ÖZ

Amaç: Bu çalışmada, yoğun bakım ünitesinde ağır COVID-19 pnömonisi nedeniyle izlenen hastalarda standart tedaviye eklenen rektal ozon insüflasyonunun klinik ve laboratuvar sonuçlara etkisinin değerlendirilmesi amaçlandı.

Gereç ve Yöntem: Tek körlü, randomize, prospektif bu çalışmaya Mayıs–Temmuz 2020 tarihleri arasında yoğun bakımda izlenen 60 ağır COVID-19 hastası dahil edildi. Hastalar rastgele rektal ozon insüflasyonu (ROI, n=30) ve kontrol (n=30) gruplarına ayrıldı. ROI grubuna standart tedaviye ek olarak 14 gün boyunca 12 saatte bir 30 µg/250 mL dozunda rektal ozon uygulandı. Birincil sonuçları CRP düzeyi, oksijen saturasyonu, GKS ve SOFA skorlarıydı. İkincil sonuçları entübasyon gereksinimi, yatış süreleri ve mortaliteydi.

Bulgular: Gruplar arasında başlangıç klinik özellikleri açısından anlamlı fark yoktu. ROI grubunda CRP düzeylerinde anlamlı azalma, GKS skorlarında artış ve SOFA skorlarında düşüş saptandı (p<0,05). Entübasyon gereksinimi ve mortalite oranı ROI grubunda kontrol grubuna kıyasla anlamlı derecede daha düşüktü (p<0,05).

Sonuç: Rektal ozon insüflasyonu, ağır COVID-19 hastalarında inflamasyonun azalmasına ve klinik iyileşmeye katkı sağlayabilecek tamamlayıcı bir tedavi seçeneği olabilir. Bulguların doğrulanması için daha geniş ölçekli çalışmalara ihtiyaç vardır.

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INTRODUCTION

Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) is a severe viral illness caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) that has become a global pandemic since December 2019 (1,2). SARS-CoV-2 enters host cells through its spike (S) protein, which binds to angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) receptors on the cell surface, initiating viral replication. In severe cases of COVID-19, a dysregulated immune response and excessive inflammation can trigger a cytokine storm, resulting in lung tissue damage, acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), and multiorgan dysfunction (3,4).

Elevated serum inflammatory markers (e.g., IL-6, IL-1 β , TNF- α) and an imbalanced immune response in severe COVID-19 have been associated with clinical deterioration. The host's intense inflammatory reaction may lead to pulmonary edema, alveolar damage, and hypoxemia, which are hallmarks of severe clinical manifestations (5).

Although antiviral therapies and immunomodulatory agents have been developed for COVID-19, no specific treatment has yet been fully established that significantly reduces mortality, particularly in severe and critically ill patients. Both antiviral drugs and immune-regulating therapies are being investigated to address this gap (6). One promising approach is ozone therapy (7).

Ozone (O $_3$), a powerful oxidant composed of three oxygen atoms, has been shown in numerous studies to have potential biological effects, including immune modulation, anti-inflammatory activity, and improvement of cellular oxygen metabolism when applied in a controlled manner (8). Clinical studies

and systematic reviews suggest that ozone therapy may reduce inflammatory markers and improve certain laboratory parameters in patients with COVID-19 (9).

Rectal ozone insufflation, a non-invasive method used as an alternative to major autohemotherapy, may provide a safer option in intensive care units by minimizing the risk of complications associated with intravenous procedures (10,11). In this study, we evaluated the effects of rectal ozone insufflation, in addition to standard therapy, on clinical and laboratory outcomes in patients with severe COVID-19 pneumonia admitted to the intensive care unit.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study Design

This study was designed as a single-blind, randomized, prospective interventional clinical trial.

Patient Selection

Patients admitted to the intensive care unit (ICU) between May 15 and July 7, 2020, and treated according to the Ministry of Health COVID-19 adult patient protocol for severe pneumonia, ARDS, sepsis, and septic shock were considered for inclusion.

Inclusion criteria:

- Age \geq 18 years
- Clinically and radiologically confirmed SARS-CoV-2 infection
- Admission to the ICU within the first 72 hours
- Presence of hypoxemia, pneumonia findings, and elevated inflammatory markers

Exclusion criteria:

- Pregnancy, postpartum period, or lactation
- Contraindications to rectal administration (anal fistula, fissure, or history of rectal surgery)
- G6PD deficiency
- Use of immunosuppressive therapy or history of organ transplantation
- Participation in another clinical trial simultaneously

Randomization and Groups

The sample size was calculated based on previous similar studies using G*Power software, with a 95% confidence level and 80% power, resulting in a minimum of 30 patients per group. A total of 60 patients were randomized into:

- Experimental (ROI) group (n=30): Patients receiving rectal ozone insufflation in addition to standard therapy
- Control group (n=30): Patients receiving standard COVID-19 therapy alone

Intervention Protocol

The ROI group received rectal ozone insufflation every 12 hours for 14 days in accordance with the International Madrid Ozone Therapy Declaration. Each session involved 250 mL of ozone gas at a concentration of 30 µg/mL, administered at a rate of 1 mL/sec.

The procedure utilized the Basic Plus ozone device, ozone-resistant silicone tubing, a 2000 mL clamp-free urine bag, and a 14-Fr rectal catheter, performed in a sterile, ventilated environment to minimize contamination risk. Patients were positioned in lateral decubitus with slight flexion of the legs during administration and returned to supine

rest afterward for observation. To prevent potential tissue injury, all patients underwent rectal examination prior to administration to rule out fistulas or prior surgical interventions.

The post-treatment follow-up period lasted 30 days from the end of therapy. Patients transferred from the ICU to the ward completed the 14-day treatment course in the ward.

Assessed Parameters

Primary endpoints:

- C-reactive protein (CRP) levels
- Oxygen saturation
- Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS)
- Sequential Organ Failure Assessment (SOFA) score

Secondary endpoints:

- Need for and duration of intubation
- ICU and hospital length of stay
- Mortality rate

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS software. Continuous variables were expressed as mean ± standard deviation or median (interquartile range, IQR). Normality was assessed using the Shapiro–Wilk test. For normally distributed variables, comparisons between two groups were performed with the independent t-test, and for non-normally distributed variables, the Wilcoxon test was used for time-dependent comparisons and the Mann–Whitney U test for between-group comparisons. Categorical variables were analyzed using the chi-square test. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Approval

The study was approved by the Clinical Research Ethics Committee of SBÜ Bağıcılar Training and Research Hospital (Decision No: 2020.05.2.15.071). The study was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki. Written informed consent was obtained from all patients or their legal guardians.

RESULTS

The demographic characteristics and clinical findings of the patients at ICU admission are presented in Table 1. A total of 60 patients were included in the study and were divided into two groups: the experimental group receiving rectal ozone insufflation (ROI group, n=30) and the control group receiving standard COVID-19 therapy alone (n=30).

The age range of participants in the ROI group was 37–96 years, with a mean age of 71.10 ± 15.47 years. In the control group, the age range was 38–91 years, with a mean age of 66.50 ± 13.24 years. Females comprised 56.67% (n=17) of the ROI group and 53.33% (n=16) of the control group. No statistically significant differences were observed between the groups in terms of age, sex distribution, or comorbid conditions (except for arrhythmia, vitamin D deficiency, and BPH) ($p > 0.05$).

The pre-specified primary and secondary outcome measures were analyzed to evaluate the contribution of rectal ozone therapy.

During the ICU stay, patients' body temperatures ranged between 36–37 °C in both groups, likely due to the administration of anti-inflammatory and antipyretic treatments, and no significant differences were observed between the groups.

To maintain oxygen saturation between

90–100% in patients with severe COVID-19 pneumonia, various oxygen delivery methods were applied, including nasal cannula, mask, CPAP, intubation, and tracheostomy. As no substantial variation in oxygen saturation was observed between the groups, respiratory function was assessed based on the need for and duration of intubation.

No significant difference was found between the groups regarding the number of days requiring intubation ($p = 0.684$), nor in the number of days not requiring intubation ($p = 0.113$). However, the number of patients requiring intubation was significantly lower in the experimental group compared to the control group ($p = 0.007$). Moreover, the number of patients successfully extubated was significantly higher in the experimental group ($p = 0.002$).

The mean hospital length of stay was significantly longer in the experimental group compared to the control group ($p = 0.029$). In contrast, no significant difference was observed in ICU length of stay ($p = 0.182$).

Mortality in the control group was 70% (n=21), whereas in the experimental group it was 43.3% (n=13). The mortality rate in the experimental group was significantly lower compared to the control group ($p = 0.037$) (Table 1).

CRP levels were measured on the third day of hospitalization and at discharge. No statistically significant difference was observed in baseline CRP levels between the control and experimental groups ($p = 0.859$), nor in CRP levels at discharge ($p = 0.110$). In the control group, no significant changes were detected between baseline and discharge CRP levels ($p = 0.835$). In contrast, the experimental group demonstrated a significant reduction in CRP levels at discharge compared to baseline ($p = 0.001$).

Table 1. Demographic and clinical characteristics of the patients

Variable		Control group	Ozone group	p
Age (years)	Mean±SD	66,50±13,24	71,10±15,47	0,221*
Sex	Female	n=16 53,33%	n=17 56,67%	0,795+
	Male	n=14 46,67%	n=13 43,33%	
Hospital length of stay (days)	Mean±SD	12,1±6,94	21,13±17,64	0,029‡
	Median (IQR)	11 (6-17,25)	15 (9,75-26)	
ICU length of stay (days)	Mean±SD	9,17±5,68	16,1±17,36	0,182‡
	Median (IQR)	9 (5,75-12)	10 (6-17,25)	
ICU intubation days	Mean±SD	7,63±5,54	8,5±7,46	0,684‡
	Median (IQR)	6 (3-12)	6,5 (5-9)	
ICU extubation days	Mean±SD	4,91±2,77	9,75±8,88	0,113‡
	Median (IQR)	4 (2-7)	7,5 (3,25-13,5)	
Number of intubated patients in ICU		n=27 90,00%	n=18 60,00%	0,007+
Number of extubated patients in ICU		n=11 36,67%	n=23 76,67%	0,002+
Vitamin D (ng/mL)	Mean±SD	16,73±14,72	19,02±13,1	0,318‡
	Median (IQR)	12,49 (5,53-27,74)	16,91 (8,2-26,19)	
Diabetes mellitus (DM)		n=19 63,33%	n=17 56,67%	0,598+
Hypertension (HT)		n=16 53,33%	n=15 50,00%	0,796+
COPD–Asthma		n=3 10,00%	n=5 16,67%	0,448+
Heart failure (HF)		n=2 6,67%	n=6 20,00%	0,129+
Chronic kidney disease (CKD)		n=5 16,67%	n=3 10,00%	0,448+
Arrhythmia		n=0 0,00%	n=7 23,33%	0,005+
Alzheimer's disease		n=4 13,33%	n=8 26,67%	0,197+
Vitamin D deficiency		n=7 23,33%	n=1 3,33%	0,023+
Coronary artery disease (CAD)		n=3 10,00%	n=2 6,67%	0,640+
Benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH)		n=0 0,00%	n=7 23,33%	0,005+
Other comorbidities		n=3 10,00%	n=8 26,67%	0,095+
Death		n=21 70,00%	n=13 43,33%	0,037+

*Independent t-test; ‡Mann–Whitney U test; +Chi-square test

No significant difference was observed in baseline GCS scores between the control and experimental groups ($p = 0.793$). At discharge, the experimental group exhibited significantly

higher mean GCS scores compared to the control group ($p = 0.012$). While no significant changes in GCS were detected between baseline and discharge in the control group

(p = 0.294), the experimental group showed a significant increase in GCS scores at discharge relative to baseline (p = 0.0001).

Baseline SOFA scores did not differ significantly between the control and experimental groups (p = 0.262). Similarly, no significant differences were observed in SOFA scores at discharge (p = 0.759). While no significant changes occurred between baseline and discharge SOFA scores in the control group (p = 0.901), the experimental group demonstrated a significant decrease in SOFA scores at discharge compared to baseline (p = 0.007) (Table 2).

in the ozone group (p = 0.035), indicating a positive effect of ozone therapy on the level of consciousness. No significant differences were observed between the groups in terms of SOFA scores (p = 0.441), suggesting that changes in organ function were similar in both groups. Overall, rectal ozone therapy demonstrated a particularly beneficial impact on consciousness levels.

Table 2. CRP, GCS, and SOFA parameters in the control and rectal ozone groups

		Control group	Ozone group	p‡	
CRP (mg/L)	Baseline	Mean±SD	159,17±111,67		
		Median (IQR)	151 (87,5-228,25)	143,5 (80,25-225,25)	0,859
	Discharge	Mean±SD	154,41±125,85	91,38±66,12	
		Median (IQR)	129,5 (61,38-244,25)	91 (16-155,25)	0,110
	p†		0,835	0,001	
	GCS	Baseline	Mean±SD	5,5±1,78	6,37±3,41
Median (IQR)			5 (4-7)	5 (3,75-8,25)	0,793
Discharge		Mean±SD	6,53±5,51	9,03±5,07	
		Median (IQR)	3 (3-15)	8,5 (3,75-15)	0,012
p†		0,294	0,0001		
SOFA		Baseline	Mean±SD	6,3±2,63	5,73±2,65
	Median (IQR)		7 (4-8)	5 (4-7)	0,262
	Discharge	Mean±SD	5,31±5,42	4,5±3,14	
		Median (IQR)	3 (1,5-10)	4 (2-6)	0,759
	p†		0,901	0,007	

‡ Mann–Whitney U test †Wilcoxon test

CRP: C-reactive protein, GCS: Glasgow Coma Scale, SOFA: Sequential Organ Failure Assessment

Table 3 presents the changes in CRP, GCS, and SOFA scores from baseline to discharge in the control and rectal ozone groups. Although the decrease in CRP was greater in the ozone group compared to the control group, this difference did not reach statistical significance (p = 0.130). In contrast, GCS scores showed a significant improvement

DISCUSSION

In this study, the effects of rectal ozone insufflation added to standard therapy were evaluated in patients with severe COVID-19 pneumonia admitted to the intensive care unit (ICU). The findings suggest that ozone therapy may provide beneficial effects, particularly in reducing inflammation, improving

Table 3. Baseline–discharge changes in CRP, GCS, and SOFA parameters in the control and rectal ozone groups

		Control group	Ozone group	p‡
CRP (mg/L)	Mean±SD	4,73±124,49	59,33±90,11	
baseline–discharge change	Median (IQR)	16 (-59,75-105,5)	34 (-7,75-150,75)	0,130
GCS baseline–discharge change	Mean±SD	-1,03±5,29	-2,67±3,25	
	Median (IQR)	1 (-8-2)	-2,5 (-5-0)	0,035
SOFA baseline–discharge change	Mean±SD	0,15±4,38	1,23±2,31	
	Median (IQR)	0 (-3-3,5)	0 (0-3)	0,441

‡Mann Whitney U test

CRP: C-reactive protein, GCS: Glasgow Coma Scale, SOFA: Sequential Organ Failure Assessment

neurological status, enhancing organ failure scores, decreasing the need for intubation, and lowering mortality rates.

Systematic reviews and meta-analyses investigating ozone therapy have focused on its use in viral infections, including COVID-19 (12,13). In cases where ozone was used as an adjuvant therapy, inflammatory markers such as CRP, IL-6, and D-dimer were observed to decrease. However, most of these studies were retrospective or observational rather than randomized controlled trials, and evidence regarding clinical outcomes remains inconsistent (14,15). One systematic review reported improvements in laboratory parameters with ozone therapy, but failed to demonstrate consistent benefits regarding clinical outcomes such as mortality, ICU stay, or hospital length of stay (9).

Severe clinical progression in COVID-19 is associated with exaggerated inflammatory responses and cytokine storm (7). CRP has been recognized as an important biomarker for predicting mortality in sepsis and severe COVID-19 (16,17), and in ICU patients, CRP measured on the third day of admission has been reported as a stronger prognostic indicator than baseline values (18). In our study, a significant decrease in CRP levels was observed in the ozone group, suggesting

that ozone therapy may modulate the inflammatory response.

The anti-inflammatory effects of ozone have been attributed to the activation of nuclear factor erythroid 2–related factor 2 (Nrf2) pathways and suppression of pro-inflammatory cytokine production. These mechanisms have been highlighted in previous studies investigating ozone therapy in COVID-19 patients (9, 11).

In critically ill patients, clinicians frequently use scoring systems to objectively assess neurological function and organ dysfunction, which are critical for both prognostic prediction and monitoring treatment response. GCS evaluates consciousness through eye-opening, verbal, and motor responses. Low GCS scores are associated with worse clinical outcomes and higher mortality, particularly in severe infections or systemic injury. Several ICU studies have demonstrated that GCS-based neurological assessment strongly correlates with short-term mortality (19). SOFA score evaluates dysfunction in six organ systems—respiratory, cardiovascular, hepatic, coagulation, renal, and neurological—in a standardized manner. In the context of COVID-19, elevated SOFA scores at hospital admission have been linked to increased disease severity and mortality, making

SOFA a valuable prognostic index in severe SARS-CoV-2 infection (20). The combined use of GCS and SOFA allows comprehensive assessment of neurological status and multi-organ involvement and is routinely integrated into clinical protocols to guide treatment decisions and prognostication in critically ill patients. In our study, improvements in GCS and SOFA scores support the beneficial effects of ozone therapy on systemic organ function and neurological status. A reduction in SOFA score indicates a decreased risk of multi-organ failure, which is clinically relevant for both sepsis and COVID-19 prognosis.

The observed reductions in intubation requirements and mortality rates suggest that ozone therapy may indirectly but meaningfully contribute to respiratory function and overall clinical course. Similarly, previous studies have reported that ozone therapy may reduce mortality in COVID-19 patients (9,21).

Some clinical reports indicate that rectal ozone administration may enhance gas exchange, improve oxygen saturation, and reduce the need for respiratory support. However, these data are based on small patient cohorts, limiting generalizability (11). In our study, the lower requirement for intubation and higher number of successfully extubated patients are consistent with this potential physiologic effect, although the possibility that these findings occurred by chance cannot be excluded.

The longer hospital stay observed in the ozone group may reflect that these patients successfully overcame the ICU phase and entered a prolonged clinical recovery period, which is not considered a negative outcome when interpreted alongside reduced mortality rates.

The existing literature generally indicates that ozone therapy is safe, with limited data

on serious adverse effects (21). In our study, no adverse events were reported following ozone therapy, supporting its favorable safety profile. It is important to note that ozone must be administered in controlled doses, as improper application can potentially cause oxidative damage and toxicity.

In conclusion, this study demonstrates that rectal ozone insufflation added to standard therapy in ICU patients with severe COVID-19 pneumonia reduces inflammatory markers, improves GCS and SOFA scores, decreases the need for intubation, and lowers mortality. These findings suggest that rectal ozone insufflation may be a safe and potentially effective adjunctive treatment option. Nonetheless, confirmation of these results requires larger, multicenter, randomized controlled trials.

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